

Climate Models with Delay Differential Equations

Hedson Malata (hedson.malata@aims.ac.rw)
African Institute for Mathematical Sciences (AIMS) Rwanda

Supervised by: Prof Mohamed MBEHOU
University of Yaounde I, Cameroon

May, 2020

Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of a Master of Science in Mathematical Sciences at AIMS Rwanda

AIMS

African Institute for
Mathematical Sciences
RWANDA

Abstract

Delay differential equations are types of differential equations where the derivative of the given unknown function at certain times is given in terms of the values of the function at previous times.

In this study, conceptual climate models have been addressed as delay processes and numerical methods used in solving delay differential equations. A particular tool called the pydelay has been used in solving a particular conceptual climate model called energy balance model.

Declaration

I, the undersigned, hereby declare that the work contained in this research project is my original work, and that any work done by others or by myself previously has been acknowledged and referenced accordingly.

Hedson Malata, May 2020

Contents

Abstract	i
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Study objectives	2
2 LITERATURE REVIEW	3
2.1 Challenges faced when using complex models to make weather predictions.	3
2.2 Importance of conceptual climate models.	3
2.3 Introduction to delay differential equations and the methods of steps	4
2.4 Importance of delay differential equations on conceptual climate models	9
2.5 Energy-balance models (EBMs)	10
3 Methodology	12
3.1 Haar Wavelet	12
3.2 Introductions to pydelay program	18
4 Analysis	20
4.1 Analysis of some delay differential equations	20
4.2 Analysis of the energy balance model	21
5 Discussions	23
5.1 Discussions of some delay differential equations	23
5.2 Discussion of the energy balance model	23
6 Conclusion and Future Work	24
6.1 Conclusion	24
6.2 Further Work	24
7 Appendix	25
References	34

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

According to [Wikipedia contributors \(2020a\)](#), climate is defined as the long-term average of weather at a given location whereas climate change is defined as the visible changes in climate that continues for a certain period of time, such as decades, centuries etc. Therefore, according to [Parker \(2018\)](#), climate science seeks to investigate the structure and dynamical system of the Earth's climate. Studying climate science has significantly opened ways of understanding how the overview of the Earth's climate, that is, the global, regional and local climates are maintained as well as the processes by which they change over time. While people have always tried to predict the weather, this branch of science has gained in importance since it has been discovered that it is useful in addressing the challenges of climate change.

In order to understand the climate and to be able to take decisions that will mitigate the impact of our human activity on the climate, models for example, the general circulation models, have been developed to be able to explain and predict changes in the climate. The general circulation model is a type of climate model which uses a mathematical model called the general circulation of planetary atmosphere or ocean. The general circulation model uses the Navier-Stokes equations to make weather predictions ([Rakshit et al., 2020](#)).

Since climate models need to simplify the complex interactions between the parts of a very complex system, no model can be perfectly accurate. Every climate model, even if all the necessary data and all the mathematical equations are available, it would be too complex to solve, so we have to use approximate methods, which requires a large amount of time and computing power.

In order to use the large but finite amount of computing power efficiently, climate scientists are increasingly developing and employing what are known as *conceptual models*, which do not try to represent the whole of the atmosphere or even a limited region of it, but instead investigate the effects of the key mechanisms of the system, which can be described in equations that are relatively simple and can be solved in the time and with the means available. These conceptual climate can be described by feedback mechanisms (which can be positive or negative) through which the system variables are related and interact with each other.

According to [Wikipedia contributors \(2020c\)](#), as early as the 19th century, climate scientists around the globe have been studying climate change, due to observations made when there was a change in ice ages, in rain distribution pattern and other natural changes in paleoclimate were suspected and the greenhouse effects were identified. Understanding and making predictions of how climate will change over the next period of time is imperative in planning and preparing adequately for their effects. Making climate predictions is not only important for the economy of the country but also for the society. This has led to the study of how natural and human factors can affect climate and what these effects may impact the future, and how nations around the globe can prepare in case they strike. In order to model climate, different modeling methods such as the general circulation models have been developed. Due to the limitations in time and computing power of the general circulation models, we look at how conceptual climate models, which do not try to represent the whole of the atmosphere which can be described by relatively simple equations, can be used in a branch of mathematics known as delay differential equation to make weather and climate predictions.

1.2 Study objectives

The main objectives of this study are:

- To introduce the basics of delay differential equations, numerical analysis and their importance in conceptual climate models.
- To introduce the energy balance model as a delay process
- To analyze the given energy balance model numerically.

In this study, a particular mathematical method will be discussed that has been found useful in working with conceptual climate models. So in Chapter 2, the basic ideas underlying delay differential equations will be introduced by way of reviewing the literature on that topic, and in Chapter 3 the numerical methods and tool needed to solve them will be demonstrated. Then in Chapter 4 the ideas and methods of the previous chapters will be applied to the energy balance model that is part of various conceptual climate models.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to [MarcR.Roussel \(2005\)](#), mathematical modelling is an abstract model in which mathematical concepts and language is used to describe the behaviour of a given system. In climate science, mathematical modelling is used to model climate. Mathematical models are used to make climate and weather predictions and may take various forms.

According to [Guest Blogger \(2020\)](#), climate models predicts how average conditions changes in a given region over a given time. These climate models provides a way to test hypothesis and draw conclusions on the past, present and the future climate system. In climate science, scientists use climate models to understand Earth's climate system.

2.1 Challenges faced when using complex models to make weather predictions.

A number of known existing forecasting climate models are derived from complex models, for example the general circulation model. According to [MarcR.Roussel \(2005\)](#), a model is said to be complex if its behaviour is fundamentally difficult to model the interactions that occur between its variables. Models that are complex have distinct properties such as non-linearity, feedback loop, spontaneous order and so on.

Although the use of complex models such as the general circulation models to make weather predictions is currently common, it suffers major challenges such as large time complexity and they need good machines, that is, machines with good computing powers to make simulations ([Stocker and Knutti, 2003](#)). It was found by [Buytaert et al. \(2009\)](#) that due to the fact that complex models often have millions of variables and parameters, they are known to contain multiple errors due to wrong assumptions that are made about climate processes, limited dimensional and temporal resolutions. They are known to contain multiple errors due to the simplification of climate descriptions. According [Austin Gorens \(2020\)](#), all models must simplify a very complex climate system. This is, as a result of the lack of understanding of existing climate systems, and partly the results of computational restraints. This simplification maybe achieved in terms of spatial conditionality and time resolution, or through parameterization of the process that are simulated. In parameterization, a process is included as a simplified function instead of an explicit calculation from the first principle. Simplifying a climate model leads to the limited degrees of freedom in a simplified model. This limitation in degrees of freedom leads to underestimating natural variability which in turn leads to a general bias towards deterministic interpretations in explaining mechanism of climate change as variability plays an essential role in climate change as showed by [Stocker and Knutti \(2003\)](#).

2.2 Importance of conceptual climate models.

According to [Wilks \(2008\)](#), conceptual climate models are mathematical representations of climate processes which are useful as their working can be easily understood. These models are designed in order to investigate the interaction of processes in climate system, in this way, the equations are simplified and can easily be analysed mathematically. Conceptual climate models are characterized by positive and negative mechanism, which increases or reduces respectively any changes of system variables. In climate system, feedback loop occurs naturally on a variety of a time scale, in most cases, they occur as a result of mass or energy transport across the globe and throughout the atmosphere. For example, the energy

balance models which focuses on the global balance between the incoming and outgoing radiation on the Earth (Keane and Postlethwaite, 2017). The global temperature of the Earth is dependent upon the albedo of the Earth. Albedo, according to Robinove et al. (1981) is defined as the percentage of incoming radiation reflected from the ground into space without being absorbed. The albedo is related to the level of snow/ice cover, which depends on the global temperature. According to Keane and Postlethwaite (2017), the values of albedo depends on the past, present and future thus making it easier to make predictions about the climate system by providing understanding of the rising of the sea-level response to emission (Schleussner et al., 2011).

Conceptual climate models are imperative in predicting how the stability of a climate system is versus the global climate change. Understanding the stability of the climate system is important in making predictions about the stability of the climate system, as failure to do so may greatly affect the natural and socio-economic system, even with the current rate of change in the global temperature for example the stabilization of carbon dioxide at 450 and 550 ppm(parts per million) may possibly avoid some critical adverse thresholds (Epstein and McCarthy, 2004). Conceptual models are also useful in understanding major changes in climate patterns which are driven by the changes in positions of climate arrangements when the position of the continent changes. These models have also proved to be stronger, that is the climate arrangement are almost the same as those predicted by numerical models for a given geological period (Parrish, 1993).

According to Kuang (1993), most processes in climate dynamics takes more time to complete. Processes such as El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) which is defined as a repeated pattern in climate involving changes in the temperature of waters in the central and eastern tropical Pacific Ocean (U.S National Weather Service, 2020) takes about three to seven years to complete. While other processes such as acceleration and deceleration takes less time to complete. Therefore, it is of important to describe these processes into mathematical models of climate dynamics. These process times are referred to as delay times, and the mathematical equations that govern these delay times are referred to as **delay differential equations** (Kuang, 1993).

Conceptual climate models are characterized by feedback loops. These feedback loops are characterized by positive and negative loops. Examples of conceptual climate models includes the energy balance model. According to Keane and Postlethwaite (2017), energy balance models have feedback loops since the global temperature of the Earth depends on the albedo. Albedo does not depend only on the present temperatures alone but also on the past temperatures. As such, there is a delay in reaction of the system in the order of 1000 to 10000 years. Due to these delayed effects of feedback loops, the mathematical model which incorporates such models takes the form of delay differential equations.

2.3 Introduction to delay differential equations and the methods of steps

In this section, delay differential equations are introduced at a theoretical level as described and studied by Lynch (2018).

2.3.1 Definition. A delay differential equation subject to constant delays is of the form:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{x}(t - \tau_1), \mathbf{x}(t - \tau_2), \dots, \mathbf{x}(t - \tau_N)), \quad (2.3.1)$$

where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathfrak{R}^n$ and the delays τ_i are positive constants.

In order to solve delay differential equations, an initial history function is defined on the interval $[-\tau, 0]$. The history function determines the behaviour of the dynamical system $\mathbf{x}(t)$, assuming that the system start at $t = 0$. The simplest method for solving delay differential equations analytically is known as the **method of steps (or method of successive integration)**. The main difference between ordinary differential equations and the delay differential equations is that the solution for the delay differential equations are thought to be a mapping from the function on an interval $[t - \tau, t]$ onto an interval $[t, t + \tau]$.

2.3.2 Example. Solve the simple linear delay differential equation given by

$$\dot{x} = -x(t - 1), \quad (2.3.2)$$

with initial history function $x(t) = 1$, on $[-1, 0]$.

Solutions. Suppose that we have

$$x(t) = \phi_{i-1}(t_i),$$

over some intervals

$$[t_i - 1, t_i].$$

Then, over the interval

$$[t_i, t_i + 1],$$

by separation of variables, then

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\phi_{i-1}(t_i)}^{x(t)} dx' &= - \int_{t_i}^t \phi_{i-1}(t' - 1) dt' \\ \therefore x(t) = \phi_i(t) &= \phi_{i-1}(t_i) - \int_{t_i}^t \phi_{i-1}(t' - 1) dt'. \end{aligned}$$

Using the above formula, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= -x(t - 1) \quad \text{given the constant initial data:} \\ x(t) &= 1 \quad \text{for } t \in [-1, 0]. \end{aligned}$$

Solving this problem in the interval $[0, 1]$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= 1 - \int_0^t 1 dt' \\ &= 1 - t. \end{aligned}$$

In the interval $[1, 2]$,

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= (1 - 1) - \int_1^t (1 - (t' - 1)) dt' \\ &= - \left[2t' - \frac{t'^2}{2} \right]_1^t \\ &= -2t + \frac{t^2}{2} + \frac{3}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

On the interval $-1 \leq t \leq 10$, the above equation can be solved numerically to obtain the following numerical solutions:

Figure 2.1: The numerical solution $x(t)$ for the delay differential Equation (2.3.2).

In the following example, we look at one of the applications of delay differential equation in biology.

2.3.3 Example. In this example, we discuss the hematopoiesis model. Hematopoiesis is a biological process by which all cellular components of blood and blood plasma are produced in the body in the hematopoietic system. In this example, a one-dimensional Mackay-Glass model related to hematopoiesis defined by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{\beta x(t - \tau)}{1 + x(t - \tau)^n} - \delta x(t), \quad (2.3.3)$$

is considered, where $x(t)$ is the cell population at time t , τ is a constant time lag, and n is positive constant. The first term in the right-hand side of Equation (2.3.3) models the delayed production rate of the blood cells and δ is a death rate of blood cells.

Solving this numerically in python using the pydelay solver, the numerical solution shown in Figure (2.2) is obtained: From the numerical solutions given in Figure (2.2), with the delay term $\tau = 3$, the solution approaches the stable critical point at $x^* = 40$.

When $\tau = 15$, the numerical solution shows that there is an oscillation in the solution as given in Figure (2.3)

Figure 2.2: Asymptotic stability of the blood cell population model for Equation (2.3.3) for $\beta = 2, n = 10, \tau = 3, \delta = 0.8$.

Figure 2.3: Periodic behaviour in the blood cell population model for Equation (2.3.3) for $\beta = 2, n = 10, \tau = 15, \delta = 0.8$.

2.3.4 Linear stability Analysis. Here the linear stability of ordinary differential equations is introduced and then extended to the delay differential equations. Consider an autonomous differential equation of the form

$$\dot{x} = f(x^*), \tag{2.3.4}$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

2.3.5 Definition. A critical point is the point that satisfies the equation $\dot{x} = f(x^*) = 0$. If a solution starts at this point, it remains there forever.

2.3.6 Definition. A critical point, say, x^* , of the differential Equation (2.3.4) is said to be stable if for every $\epsilon > 0$, there is a $\delta > 0$, such that for all $t \geq t_0$,

$\|x_0 - x^*\| < \delta$ with $x_0 = x(t_0)$ implies that

$\|x(t) - x^*\| < \epsilon$, where $x(t)$ is a solution of the Equation (2.3.4).

A critical point that is not stable is said to be unstable critical point.

Let x^* be a critical point of $\dot{x} = f(x^*)$, $x \in \mathfrak{R}$. Consider a small perturbation, say, $\xi(t)$, away from the critical point at x^* to give $x(t) = x^* + \xi(t)$. A simple analysis is now applied to determine whether the perturbation grows or decays as time evolves. Now

$$\dot{\xi}(t) = \dot{x} = f(x^*) \approx f(x^* + \xi),$$

and taking the Taylor series expansion,

$$\dot{\xi} = f(x^*) + \xi f'(x^*) + \frac{\xi^2}{2!} f''(x^*) + \frac{\xi^3}{3!} f'''(x^*) + \frac{\xi^4}{4!} f^{(iv)}(x^*) + \dots$$

Applying the linear stability analysis, all the non-linear terms are ignored so that

$$\dot{\xi} = \xi f'(x^*), \quad \text{since } f(x^*) = 0.$$

Therefore, the perturbation $\xi(t)$ grows exponentially. If $f'(x^*) = 0$, then higher order derivatives must be considered to determine the stability of the critical point.

As with the ordinary differential equations, the same method is used in determining the location and stability of critical points for delay differential equations except that for delay differential equations, the solution space is an infinite-dimensional functional space unlike the ordinary differential equations with finite functional dimensional space. Using the same methods described for ordinary differential equations, a small perturbations from equilibrium can be considered in an infinite space, then the displacements are time dependent functions, $\delta x(t)$, which can persist for an interval at least the maximum value of τ_i . For simplifications of notations, write

$$\mathbf{x}_\tau = \mathbf{x}(t - \tau).$$

Using the methods similar to the one described above, suppose that

$$x = x^* + \delta x,$$

taking the Taylor series and linearisation, the following results are obtained

$$\delta \dot{\mathbf{x}} \approx \mathbf{J}_0 \delta \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{J}_{\tau_1} \delta \mathbf{x}_{\tau_1} + \dots + \mathbf{J}_{\tau_n} \delta \mathbf{x}_{\tau_n}, \quad (2.3.5)$$

where \mathbf{J}_{τ_i} are the Jacobian matrices corresponding to the matrices \mathbf{x}_{τ_i} . If the delay differential equation have exponential solutions as that of the ordinary differential equation, then

$$\delta \mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{A} e^{\lambda t},$$

where λ is an eigenvalue of the Jacobian matrix. Substituting this into (2.3.5), the following expression is obtained:

$$\lambda \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A} (\mathbf{J}_0 + e^{-\lambda \tau_1} \mathbf{J}_{\tau_1} + \dots + e^{-\lambda \tau_n} \mathbf{J}_{\tau_n}).$$

Then the characteristic equation is then given by

$$|\mathbf{J}_0 + e^{-\lambda \tau_1} \mathbf{J}_{\tau_1} + \dots + e^{-\lambda \tau_n} \mathbf{J}_{\tau_n} - \lambda \mathbf{I}| = 0,$$

where \mathbf{I} is an identity matrix. Expanding out the determinant leads to a polynomial which includes some terms in $e^{\lambda \tau_i}$ and these polynomials obtained are called the quasi-polynomials.

2.3.7 Example. Investigate the logistic delay differential equation given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \mu x(t)(1 - x(t - \tau_1)), \quad (2.3.6)$$

with the initial history function $x(t) = 0.1$, on $[-1, 0]$, $\tau_1 = 1$, as the parameter μ varies.

Solution.

For the system in 2.3.6, there are two critical points at $x^* = 0$ and $x^* = 1$. The critical point $x^* = 0$ is unstable. Now, consider the critical point $x^* = 1$. The characteristic equation is then given as

$$\mu e^{-\lambda\tau_1} + \lambda = 0. \quad (2.3.7)$$

For the critical point $x^* = 1$ to be stable, the complex roots of Equation (2.3.7) must lie on the left half of the λ plane. A Hopf bifurcation is a local bifurcation in which a critical point loses stability as a pair of complex conjugate eigenvalues cross the imaginary axis. Therefore, a bifurcation takes place when the roots lie on the imaginary axis. If $\lambda = 0 + iy$ then Equation (2.3.7) becomes

$$\mu e^{-iy\tau_1} + iy = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \mu(\cos(y\tau_1) - i \sin(y\tau_1)) + iy = 0. \quad (2.3.8)$$

Simplifying this, we have

$$\mu \cos(y\tau_1) = 0, \quad y - \mu \sin(y\tau_1) = 0.$$

The first equation has the solution $y\tau_1 = \frac{(2n+1)\pi}{2}$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, and the minimum order solution is found when $n = 0$, giving $\mu\tau_1 = \frac{\pi}{2}$. Hence, a necessary and sufficient condition for the critical point at $x^* = 1$ to be stable is $\mu\tau_1 < \frac{\pi}{2}$, and when $\mu\tau_1 \geq \frac{\pi}{2}$, the critical point goes through a bifurcation and becomes unstable and a small-amplitude limit cycle bifurcates from the critical point.

2.4 Importance of delay differential equations on conceptual climate models

The use of delay differential equations in conceptual climate models has some advantages, such as:

- Provisions of accuracy description of some processes in the conceptual model: Some of the processes of the conceptual model are accurately described by delay differential equations, for example, in engineering, accuracy of a model is essential (Keane and Postlethwaite, 2017). This is important as it may help the model to function efficiently. As showed by Kyrychko and Hogan (2010), due to the demand for precise predictions, control and performance, there is a need for models to have a much closer precision to the real system being modelled. In neural networks, Kyrychko and Hogan (2010) showed that there is a need for the model to be accurate to avoid instability and possible damages. In order to achieve this accuracy, the delay differential equations are used in conceptual climate models.
- The use of DDEs in conceptual climate model gives the best description of the behaviour of interest with the least number of variables and parameters: According to Keane and Postlethwaite (2017), the behaviour of interest in the model is described with the least number of variables and parameters, therefore, representing a conceptual model with the aid of delay differential equation helps to have a reduced model in terms variables and parameters.

- Delay differential equations can be simple enough to be responsive mathematical analysis: Delay differential equations can be simple enough and open to mathematical analysis such as linear stability analysis and bifurcation evaluation with advanced numerical tools. Most of the climate models are complex and difficult to analyse. This analysis is simplified when the model is incorporated with DDEs.

2.5 Energy-balance models (EBMs)

In this study, the goal is to know how delay differential equations are used in the energy-balance model. Delay differential equations were first used in energy balance model by Ghil and Bhattacharya (1979). In their study, the delay term was not derived mathematically, but it was introduced by following the previous studies that suggested a time lag between the Earth's surface temperature and global ice volume (Bhattacharya et al., 1982). In this study, the simplest type of energy balance model is considered, where the Earth is approximated as a single point in space, T represents the average global surface temperature. Mathematically, this is a one dimensional model since it has one variable $T(t)$, but in climate science, it is a zero dimensional model since it has no spatial dimensions. Spatial dimension according to MarcR.Roussel (2005), refers to a particular point in space in which movements can be made such as forward/backward, upward/downward, left/right. Energy balance models try to predict the average surface temperature of the Earth from the solar radiation, Earth's energy absorption and greenhouse effects.

We start by looking at the equation governing the evolution in time of T , the annually averaged temperature of the Earth's atmosphere is a system given as

$$C_0 \frac{dT}{dt} = Q_0[1 - \alpha(T)] - \sigma g(T)T^4, \quad (2.5.1)$$

where $C_0 = 1.52 \times 10^8 Jm^{-2}K^{-1}$ is the globally averaged heat capacity, $Q_0 = 349.7 Wm^{-2}$ is the mean solar radiative input, and $\sigma = 5.67 \times 10^{-8} Wm^{-2}K^{-4}$ is the Stephan Boltzmann constant. The function

$$g(T) = [1 - m \tanh(\frac{T}{T_0})^6], \quad (2.5.2)$$

is the effective emissivity coefficient of the system with attenuation coefficient constant m given as $m = 0.5$, $T_0 = 284.15K$ and the function $\alpha(T)$ is the Earth's albedo. It was found by Budyko and Sellers in Sellers (1969), who used latitudinal varying parameters of the albedo which was based on the differences in reflective properties between the ice-snow and sea-land that small values of local temperature were associated with a high constant values of the albedo, and a large enough values of temperature was associated with the low constant of the albedo. It is through their work that $\alpha(T)$ is assumed to be defined as follows:

$$\alpha(T) = \begin{cases} 0.85, & T \leq 0 \\ 2.798 - 0.009T, & 216 < T < 283 . \\ 0.25, & 283 \leq T \end{cases} \quad (2.5.3)$$

The hypothesis underlying the choice of this albedo is that a temperature range exists in which the general circulation states are associated with a high degree of cloud cover that is a large albedo. The physical considerations (such as terrestrial vegetation, dust or soot) underlying the parameterization of the Equation (2.5.3) limit themselves to the surface albedo; that is, it does not put into considerations

the effects of cloud cover. According to [Andersson and Lundberg \(1988\)](#), the most important single contribution to the total albedo is controlled by the degree of cloudiness. It was for this reason that [Goody \(1980\)](#) introduced a spatially non-monotonic albedo which could be parameterized in terms of temperature. He summarized the available evidence by indicating a relationship between the ice cap margin and the latitudinal bands of maximum cyclone frequency. This results incorporated high cloud coverage into a temperature-dependent albedo. The new albedo, which is a temperature dependent is then defined as follows:

$$\alpha^*(T) = \begin{cases} 0.85, & T \leq 216 \\ 2.798 - 0.009T, & 216 < T < 283 - B \\ 2.798 - 0.009T + A\{1 - \cos[2\pi(T - 283 - B)/B]\}, & 283 - B \leq T < 283 \\ 0.25, & 283 \leq T \end{cases} \quad (2.5.4)$$

Hence the upper and the lower junction for α^* are $T = 283K, T = 216K$ respectively characterized by the amplitude A and width B , where $A = 0.04$ and $B = 12K$. The amplitude corresponds to the observed annual variations of the globally averaged albedo.

The zero-dimensional energy balance model then takes the following form:

$$C_0 \dot{T}(t) = Q_0[1 - \alpha^*(T(t - \tau))] - \sigma g(T)T^4. \quad (2.5.5)$$

In this model, the function $\alpha^*(T(t - \tau))$ gives the description of how the Earth's albedo or reflectivity depends on temperature with delay τ , which is assumed to be a positive constant. The albedo parameterizes how much solar radiation is reflected back into space by the Earth's surface and the atmosphere. Q_0 is the mean solar radiative input and σ is the Stephan-Boltzmann constant. The temperature T^4 appears according to the Stephan-Boltzmann law for black body radiation and the function $g(T)$ is the parameterized emissivity coefficient.

3. Methodology

This chapter covers methodology used in numerical analysis of delay differential equations. There are various methods of solving delay differential equations numerically:

3.1 Haar Wavelet

The Haar wavelet method is one of the methods used in solving delay differential equations numerically. In this section, the Haar wavelet are introduced as studied by [Aziz and Amin \(2016\)](#). In the first case, a time-varying delay differential equations with time-delay τ in the state and control as studied by [CHUNG and SUN \(1987\)](#) is considered.

A time-varying delay differential equations with time-delay τ in the state and control is of the form:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u}(t) = a(t)u(t) + b(t)v(t) + c(t)u(t - \tau) + d(t)v(t - \tau) \\ u(0) = u_0 \\ u(t) = \phi(t), -\tau \leq t < 0. \end{cases}, \quad (3.1.1)$$

where $u(t)$ is a state function, $v(t)$ is a control function, $u(0)$ is the initial condition and $\phi(t)$ is the delay condition. Then the coefficients $a(t), b(t), c(t)$ and $d(t)$ are functions of time in the case of time-varying delay differential equations. In the case where these coefficients are constants, a time invariant delay differential equation is obtained.

The second type of delay differential equations to be considered are the linear systems of equations studied by [Kuang \(1993\)](#). These type of equations are of the form:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(t)\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{v}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t)\mathbf{u}(t - \tau) \\ \mathbf{u}(0) = \mathbf{u}_0 \\ \mathbf{u}(t) = \phi(t), \quad -\tau \leq t < 0. \end{cases} \quad (3.1.2)$$

Where $\mathbf{u}(t) = [u_1(t), \dots, u_n(t)]^T$ is an n-dimensional state vector, $A(t), B(t)$, and $F(t)$ are matrices of time function of suitable dimension, $\mathbf{v}(t) = [v_1(t), \dots, v_n(t)]^T$ is an n-dimensional control vector, \mathbf{u}_0 is the initial condition vector and $\phi(t)$ is the delay condition vector.

And the third type of delay differential equations to be considered are the delay partial differential equations. These equations are presented following the work of [Aziz and Amin \(2016\)](#), and takes the form:

$$\frac{\partial u(x, t)}{\partial t} = A(x) \frac{\partial^2 u(x, t)}{\partial x^2} + B(x) \frac{\partial u(x, t)}{\partial x} + C(x)u(x, t) + f(x, t, u(x, t - \tau)), \quad (3.1.3)$$

with the initial condition and initial history :

$$u(t, x) = \phi(x, t), t \in [t_0 - \tau, t_0],$$

and the boundary conditions:

$$u(a, t) = g_1(t), u(b, t) = g_2(t). \quad (3.1.4)$$

3.1.1 Definition. The Haar wavelet family for interval $[0,1]$ is defined as

$$h_i(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } x \in [\alpha, \beta) \\ -1 & \text{for } x \in [\beta, \gamma), i = 2, 3, \dots, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.1.5)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{m}, \beta = \frac{k + \frac{1}{2}}{m}, \gamma = \frac{k + 1}{m}.$$

In the definition above, the integer $m = 2^j, j = 0, 1, \dots, J$ shows the level of the wavelet and the integer $k = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1$ is the translation parameter. The maximum level of resolution is J and the index i is defined as $i = m + k + 1$. For the minimal values of $m = 1, k = 0$, we have $i = 2$. The maximum value of i is $i = 2M = N = 2^{J+1}$. For $i = 1$, we have $h_1(x)$, the scaling function for the family of Haar wavelet which is defined as

$$h_1(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } x \in [0, 1) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.1.6)$$

Since any square integrable function $f(x)$ defined on the half closed interval $[0, 1)$ can be expressed as an infinite sum of Haar wavelet (Aziz et al., 2010), then

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \lambda_i h_i(x).$$

For approximation purposes, the above series can be written as a finite number of terms. Thus, any square integrable function $f(x)$ defined on $[0, 1)$ can be approximated as a finite sum of Haar wavelet as follows:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i h_i(x).$$

We can introduce the following notations:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{i,1}(x) &= \int_0^x h_i(z) dz \\ p_{i,v+1}(x) &= \int_0^x p_{i,v}(z) dz, v = 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

These integrals are calculated using Equation (3.1.5) and are given as follows

$$p_{i,n}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } x \in [0, \alpha), \\ \frac{1}{n!} (x - \alpha)^n & \text{for } x \in [\alpha, \beta), \\ \frac{1}{n!} [(x - \alpha)^n - 2(x - \beta)^n] & \text{for } x \in [\beta, \gamma), \\ \frac{1}{n!} [(x - \alpha)^n - 2(x - \beta)^n + (x - \gamma)^n] & \text{for } x \in [\gamma, 1) \end{cases}, \quad (3.1.7)$$

where $n = 1, 2, \dots$.

3.1.2 Numerical methods for Haar wavelet. Suppose that $\dot{u}(t)$ is a square integrable function, then it can be expressed as a Haar wavelet series as

$$\dot{u}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i h_i.$$

Integrating this gives

$$u(t) = u_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t), \quad (3.1.8)$$

where $u_0 = u(0)$.

- **Linear case:** Consider the delay differential equation with a time delay τ in the state and control given in Equation (3.1.1). Applying the Haar wavelet approximation gives

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i h_i(t) - a(t) \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t) = \begin{cases} a(t)u_0 + b(t)v(t) + c(t)\phi(t - \tau) + d(t)v(t - \tau), & t < 0 \\ a(t)u_0 + b(t)v(t) + c(t) \left(u_0 + \sum_{i=0}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t - \tau) \right) + \\ d(t)v(t - \tau), & t > 0. \end{cases}$$

Discretizing the above equation at the collocative points t_j , where $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$, gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i h_i(t_j) - a(t_j) \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t_j) = \\ & \begin{cases} a(t_j)u_0 + b(t_j)v(t_j) + c(t_j)\phi(t_j - \tau) + d(t_j)v(t_j - \tau) & t_j < 0 \\ a(t_j)u_0 + b(t_j)v(t_j) + c(t_j) \left(u_0 + \sum_{i=0}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t_j - \tau) \right) + \\ d(t_j)v(t_j - \tau) & t_j > 0. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.9)$$

In matrix form, the above system can be written as

$$M\lambda = B \quad \text{where} \quad M = [M_{i,j}]_{N \times N}, \lambda = [\lambda_i]_{N \times 1}, B = [B_i]_{N \times 1},$$

$$M_{i,j} = \begin{cases} h_i t_j - a(t_j) p_{i,1}(t_j), & t_j < 0 \\ h_i t_j - a(t_j) p_{i,1}(t_j) - c(t_j) p_{i,1}(t_j - \tau), & t_j > 0 \end{cases}$$

$$B_j = \begin{cases} a(t_j)u_0 + b(t_j)v(t_j) + c(t_j)\phi(t_j - \tau) + d(t_j)v(t_j - \tau), & t_j < 0 \\ a(t_j)u_0 + b(t_j)v(t_j) + c(t_j) \left(u_0 + \sum_{i=0}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t_j - \tau) \right) + \\ d(t_j)v(t_j - \tau), & t_j > 0, \end{cases}$$

Therefore, $\lambda_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ can be calculated as

$$\lambda = M^{-1}B.$$

The approximate solutions at the collocation points are finally obtained by substituting $\lambda_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ in Equation (3.1.8).

- **Non linear case:** For the non-linear case, the first order non-linear delay differential equation of the following form is considered :

$$\dot{u}(t) = f(t, u(t), u(t - \tau)), \quad (3.1.10)$$

subject to initial condition and initial history:

$$\begin{aligned} u(t_0) &= u_0 \\ u(t) &= \phi(t), \quad \tau < t < 0 \end{aligned}$$

Applying Haar wavelet approximation gives:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i h_i(t) = \begin{cases} f(t, u_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t), \phi(t - \tau)), & t < 0 \\ f(t, u_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t), u_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t - \tau)), & t > 0, \end{cases}$$

Substituting the collocation points, the following system of non-linear equations are obtained:

$$\mathbf{F}_j = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i h_i(t_j) - f(t_j, u_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t_j), \phi(t_j - \tau)) = 0, & t_j < 0 \\ \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i h_i(t_j) - f(t_j, u_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t_j), u_0 + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i p_{i,1}(t_j - \tau)) = 0, & t_j > 0, \end{cases} \quad (3.1.11)$$

with $j = 1, 2, \dots, N$. The method can be solved using either Newton's method or Broyden's method. The Jacobian of the system is given by

$$\mathbf{J} = [J_{jk}]_{N \times N},$$

where

$$J_{jk} = \frac{\partial F_j}{\partial \lambda_k} = \begin{cases} h_k(t_j) - \frac{\partial f}{\partial u} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \lambda_k} = h_k(t_j) - p_{k,1}(t_j) \frac{\partial f}{\partial u} & t_j < 0 \\ h_k(t_j) - \frac{\partial f}{\partial u} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \lambda_k} = h_k(t_j) - (p_{k,1}(t_j) + p_{k,1}(t_j - \tau)) \frac{\partial f}{\partial u} & t_j > 0. \end{cases} \quad (3.1.12)$$

The solution of the above system gives values of the unknown coefficients $\lambda_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. The numerical solution is obtained in a similar manner as discussed above in the linear case.

3.1.3 Numerical Solutions of delay differential systems. Consider the linear delay differential system given in (3.1.2). Assume that

$$\dot{u}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(k)} h_i(t), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N,$$

then integrating this yields the following:

$$u_k^{(t)} = u_{k_0} + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(k)} p_{i,1}(t), \quad (3.1.13)$$

where $u_{k_0} = u_k(0)$.

With these approximations, the following vectors are obtained:

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{u}_1(t) \\ \dot{u}_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ \dot{u}_n(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(1)} h_i(t) \\ \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(2)} h_i(t) \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(n)} h_i(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t) \\ u_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ u_n(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{10} + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(1)} \mathbf{p}_{i,1}(t) \\ u_{10} + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(2)} \mathbf{p}_{i,1}(t) \\ \vdots \\ u_{10} + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(n)} \mathbf{p}_{i,1}(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$\mathbf{v}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} v_1(t) \\ v_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ v_n(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

And finally the delay term may be written as

$$\mathbf{u}(t - \tau) = \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t - \tau) \\ u_2(t - \tau) \\ \vdots \\ u_n(t - \tau) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1(t) \\ \phi_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ \phi_n(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{when } t < 0$$

and

$$\mathbf{u}(t - \tau) = \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t - \tau) \\ u_2(t - \tau) \\ \vdots \\ u_n(t - \tau) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{10} + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(1)} \mathbf{p}_{i,1}(t - \tau) \\ u_{20} + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(2)} \mathbf{p}_{i,1}(t - \tau) \\ \vdots \\ u_{n0} + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{(n)} \mathbf{p}_{i,1}(t - \tau) \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{when } t > 0$$

Substituting these in the equation

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(t)\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{v}(t) + \mathbf{F}(t)\mathbf{u}(t - \tau),$$

an $N \times N$ linear system with unknowns is obtained $\lambda_i^{(k)}, i = 1, 2, \dots, N, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ solving this linear system with any linear solver, yields values of unknown $\lambda_i^{(k)}, i = 1, 2, \dots, N, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$. The approximate solutions then can easily be recovered by substituting these unknowns in Equation (3.1.13)

3.1.4 Numerical solutions of partial delay differential equations. The second order delay partial differential equation given in Equation (3.1.3) with delay in time variable is considered. The method can easily be extended to higher order delay partial differential equations with delay in time. In this method, space derivative are approximated using Haar wavelet whereas time derivative is approximated by the finite difference method.

- **Space derivative discretization:** The highest space derivative occurring in the equation is approximated using Haar wavelet expansion as

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}(x, t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i(t) h_i(x).$$

Integrating this and using the boundary conditions given in (3.1.4), the following expressions for the first derivative and the solution $u(x, t)$ is obtained,

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}(x, t) = u(1, t) - u(0, t) + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i(t)(\mathbf{p}_{i,1}(x) - \mathbf{p}_{i,2}(1)),$$

and

$$u(x, t) = (1 - x)u(0, t) + xu(1, t) + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i(t)(\mathbf{p}_{i,2}(x) - x\mathbf{p}_{i,2}(1)).$$

- **Time derivative discretization:** Time derivative is approximated by the forward difference formula

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{u(x, t) - u(x, t - \Delta t)}{\Delta t},$$

where t is the final time at $t - \Delta t$ is the previous time.

- **Numerical scheme:** With time derivative approximation, Equation (3.1.3) becomes

$$\frac{u(x, t) - u(x, t - \Delta t)}{\Delta t} = A(x)\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + B(x)\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + C(x)u(x, t) + f(x, t, u(x, t - \tau)).$$

In order to simplify the notations, let u^{n+1} be the final time $u(x, t)$ and u^n be the previous time $u(x, t - \Delta t)$. With these notations, the above equation becomes

$$\frac{u^{n+1} - u^n}{\Delta t} = A(x)\frac{\partial^2 u^{n+1}}{\partial x^2} + B(x)\frac{\partial u^{n+1}}{\partial x} + C(x)u^{n+1}(x, t) + f(x, t, u(x, t - \tau)).$$

Shifting the unknown terms to the left and known to the right side of the equation, we obtain

$$u^{n+1} - \Delta t \left(A(x)\frac{\partial^2 u^{n+1}}{\partial x^2} + B(x)\frac{\partial u^{n+1}}{\partial x} + C(x)u^{n+1}(x, t) \right) = u^n + \Delta t f(x, t, u(x, t - \tau)).$$

Substituting the Haar wavelet approximation for the space derivatives and the known term u^{n+1} , we have

$$A - B = u^n + \Delta t f(x, t, u(x, t - \tau)). \quad (3.1.14)$$

Where

$$A = (1 - \Delta t c(x)) \left((1 - x)u(0, t) + xu(1, t) + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i(t)(\mathbf{p}_{i,2}(x)\mathbf{p}_{i,2}(1)) \right)$$

and

$$B = \Delta t A(x) \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i^{n+1} h_i(x) - \Delta t B(x) \left(u(1, t) - u(0, t) + \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i(t)(\mathbf{p}_{i,1}(x) - \mathbf{p}_{i,2}(1)) \right)$$

and λ_i^{n+1} , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ denotes the Haar coefficients at the final time. This equation is solved iteratively. In each iteration, the values of the function $u(x, t)$ at the previous time and the delay term $u(x, t - \tau)$ are known. Thus, at each iteration an $N \times N$ linear system is obtained which is solved to obtain the unknowns λ_i^{n+1} , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. These values are used to find the approximate solutions at the final time which are then used in the next iteration. In this way we can obtain the approximate solutions after any number of time steps.

3.2 Introductions to pydelay program

pydelay program is used to translate a system of delay differential equations (DDEs) into C-code and compiles and runs the code (using the `scipy weave`). As such, it is easy to implement a system of DDEs though it runs at the speed of C. The algorithm is based on the Bogacki-Shampine method as also implemented in Matlab's `dde23` (Flunkert and Schoell, 2009).

3.2.1 Defining the equations, delays and parameters. Here we look at the implementations of algorithms for solving delay differential equations as presented by Flunkert and Schoell (2009). Using a python dictionary, equations are defined within the codes, the keys are the variable names and the entry is the right hand side of the given differential equation. The string defining the equations has to be valid C expressions that is, for example, we have to use `pow(a,b)` instead of `a**b` etc.

3.2.2 Example. Implement the following equations in pydelay:

$$\begin{cases} y_1 = -y_1 y_2(t - \tau) + y_2(t - 1) \\ y_2 = a y_1 y_2(t - 2\tau) - y_2 \\ y_3 = y_2 - y_2(t - (\tau + 1)) \end{cases} \quad (3.2.1)$$

Solutions:

Using the pydelay solver, the above equations can be implemented as follows:

```
eqns = {
'y1': '-y1 * y2(t-tau) + y2(t-1.0)',
'y2': 'a * y1 * y2 (t-2*tau) - y2',
'y3': 'y2-y2(t-(tau+1))
}
```

After equations are implemented, next, parameters are also defined as follows:

```
params = {'tau1': 1.0, 'tau2': 10.0}
```

These parameters are defined in a separate dictionary where the keys are the parameter names as shown above.

3.2.3 Setting the history. The history of the variables is stored in the dictionary `dde23.hist`. The keys are the variable names and there is an additional key `'t'` for the time array of the history.

The solver is initialized as follows:

```
dde = dde23(eqns,prams),
```

the history of all variables (defined in `eqns`) is initialized to an array of length `nn=101` filled with zeros. The time array is evenly spaced in the `[-maxdelay,0]`.

The following method shows how the history function for the Equation (3.2.1) can be set:

```
initfuncs = {
'y1': lambda x: 5.0,
'y2': lambda x: 0.1,
'y3': lambda x: 1.1
}.
```

3.2.4 The solution. After the solver has run, the solution (including the history) is stored in the dictionary `dde23.sol`. The keys are again the variable names and the time 't'. Since the solver uses adaptive step size method, the solution is not sampled at regular times. To sample the solutions at regular (or other custom spaced) times, there are two functions:

`sample(tstart = None, tfinal = None, dt = None)`. Here, solutions are sampled with dt steps between $tstart$ and $tfinal$.

tstart,tfinal Start and end value of the interval to sample. If nothing is specified $tstart$ is set to zero and $tfinal$ is set to the simulation end time.

dt Sampling size used. If nothing is specified, a reasonable value is calculated. Returns a dictionary with sampled arrays. The keys are the variable names. The key 't' corresponds to the sampling times.

`sol_sp1(t)` Samples the solutions at time t .

t Array of times points on which to sample the solution.

4. Analysis

4.1 Analysis of some delay differential equations

In this chapter, the focus is on numerical solutions for delay differential equations using the pydelay solver tool.

In the numerical solution obtained in Example (2.3.2), the derivative of the function $x(t)$ is not continuous at $t = 0$. At $t > 0$, there is an arbitrary initial function which approaches the initial history $x(t)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ and for $t < 0$, the solution is governed by the differential equation given.

Consider the logistic equation in Equation (2.3.6) given as follows:

$$\dot{x} = \mu x(t)(1 - x(1 - \tau_1)),$$

it was analytically determined that the critical points are $x^* = 0$ and $x^* = 1$. The diagram in Figure (4.1) shows the numerical solutions for the logistic Equation (2.3.6) with initial history function on $[-1, 0]$ defined by $x(t) = 0.1$ for varying values of the parameter μ .

Figure 4.1: Solution of delay differential equation in Equation (2.3.6) for $\mu = 1.2, \tau = 1$.

The numerical solution shows that when $\mu = 1.2$, the initial history $x(t)$ approaches the stable critical point at $x^* = 1$.

The numerical solution below shows that when $\mu = 1.6$, the initial history $x(t)$ approaches a stable limit cycle.

Figure 4.2: Solution of delay differential equation defined in Equation (2.3.6) for $\mu = 1.6$ and $\tau = 2$.

4.2 Analysis of the energy balance model

For the globally averaged model in Equation (2.5.5), it is not possible to incorporate the asymmetric contribution of the past temperatures to the present albedo, instead, it is assumed that the albedo at all times is affected by the time lag τ , that is,

$$\alpha^*(T) = \alpha^*(T(t - \tau)).$$

From Equation (2.5.5), we write

$$\frac{dT(t)}{dt} = \frac{Q_0[1 - \alpha^*(T)] - \sigma g(T)T^4}{C_0}, \quad (4.2.1)$$

using the `pydelay` solver, with the initial history

$$T(t) = 283.15,$$

where the parameters are given by

$$Q_0 = 349.7 \text{ W m}^{-2}, \sigma = 5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-4}, C_0 = 1.52 \times 10^8 \text{ J m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1},$$

the albedo $\alpha^*(T)$ appears as defined in Equation (2.5.4) and the emissivity function $g(T)$ also appears as defined in Equation (2.5.2). We consider the analysis of the energy balance model with different delay term τ . In this analysis, we consider $\alpha^*(T) = 0.25, g(T) = 0.88$ and varying the parameter τ . In the first case, we consider $\tau = 2.41$. We see from Figure (4.3) that, as time increases, the values of albedo also increases.

⌋

Figure 4.3: The solution for the energy balance model with $\tau = 2.41$, $\alpha^*(T) = 0.25$ and $g(T) = 0.88$.

Let us consider the solutions where $T(t) < 0$:

Figure 4.4: The solution for the energy balance model with $\tau = 2.41$, $\alpha^*(T) = 0.25$ and $g(T) = 0.88$.

Here we notice that as $T(t) \rightarrow -\infty$, the values of the albedo $\alpha^*(T)$ increases as shown in Figure (4.4).

Consider $\tau = 2.95$, then the solutions are obtained as shown in Figure (4.5).

Figure 4.5: The solution for the energy balance model with $\tau = 2.95$, $\alpha^*(T) = 0.25$ and $g(T) = 0.88$.

The solution in Figure (4.5) shows that when temperature increases, the values of albedo also increases.

5. Discussions

5.1 Discussions of some delay differential equations

From the numerical solutions obtained in Figure (2.1) for Equation (2.3.2) defined as:

$$\dot{x} = -x(t-1),$$

with initial history function $x(t) = 1$ on $[-1, 0]$, the derivative function $x(t)$ is not continuous at time $t = 0$. For $t > 0$, there is an arbitrary initial function that is, the derivative function converges to the function $x(t) = 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. And for $t < 0$, the solution is governed by the differential equation, for these values of t , the solutions remains the initial history function.

Following the hematopoiesis model described by a one-dimensional Mackay - Glass model governed by the Equation (2.3.3) given as

$$\dot{x} = \frac{\beta x(t-\tau)}{1 + x(t-\tau)^n} - \delta x(t).$$

Different values of the delay term τ gives different numerical solutions. When $\tau=3$ and $\delta = 0.8$, the cell population approaches the critical point $x^* = 40$ and when $\tau = 15$, the numerical solution for the cell population gives an oscillation. In this example, we see that the delay term τ, β, δ has effects on the model under consideration since for different values of these parameters, different numerical solutions are obtained.

Further, consider the logistic equation defined in Equation (2.3.6) given as

$$\dot{x} = \mu x(t)(1 - x(t - \tau_1)).$$

From the numerical solutions obtained from this equation, it was found that when $\mu = 1.2$, the initial history function $x(t)$ approaches the critical point $x^* = 1$ and when $\mu = 1.6$, the initial history $x(t)$ approaches the stable limit cycle. Thus, for different values of τ , the logistic equation has different numerical solution.

5.2 Discussion of the energy balance model

From numerical solutions obtained in Figure (4.3) it is shown that with the delay term $\tau = 2.41$, the solutions shows that the increase in temperature decreases the values of albedo.

The term $\alpha^*(t - \tau)$ describes the effects of temperature of the Earth on albedo with the delay term τ . The values of the albedo obtained in this study agrees with the work of Sellers (1969) who used latitudinal varying parameters, and stated that small values of local temperature were associated with high constant values of albedo and large enough values of temperature were associated with small values of albedo. The relationship between temperature and albedo is defined in Equation (2.5.4).

On the other hand, from the numerical solutions obtained in Figure (4.5), it is shown that when the delay term τ increases above $\tau = 2.41$ and reduces below $\tau = 2.41$, then, there is a direct relationship between temperature and the values of albedo.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

6.1 Conclusion

In chapter three, the Haar wavelet method and the pydelay program were introduced. The Haar wavelet is one of the numerical methods used in solving delay differential equations. Under Haar wavelet, some of the numerical methods were reviewed. These numerical methods enabled us to construct some numerical solutions for the systems of delay differential equations and some of the schemes and solutions of the partial delay differential equations.

The focus of this study was to use the pydelay solver to solve delay differential equations. We have illustrated how pydelay solver can be used to solve some delay differential equations. The exploration of the climate models with delay differential equations has illustrated how conceptual climate models can be solved numerically using the numerical tools which models delay differential equations known as the pydelay solver. The pydelay solver simplifies the complex models to simple enough models and uses the available computing powers and reasonable time complexity. In this study, the basics of delay differential equations were introduced, tools and their use in conceptual climate models. The pydelay tool made it possible to solve some delay differential equations and also to incorporate an energy balance model into a delay process which further allowed us to analyse the energy balance model using pydelay program in python language. It is through this exploration that it has been determined that delay differential equations have unique solutions for different parameters. This therefore makes it difficult to have a general numerical solution due to the sensitivity nature of the pydelay since any slight change in parameters or the delay term can easily be identified through the numerical solutions, for example, the logistic equation and the hematopoiesis model cannot predict the general behaviour of solutions, that is what does the solutions become when we consider $\tau \rightarrow \infty$? The inconvenience of this tool is that it is not easy to setup in python, as such, in most cases, Matlab's dde23 solver is used.

Finally, we have looked at the applications of delay differential equation in conceptual climate model, in this case, the energy balance model. The numerical solutions were calculated for different values of τ . Our conclusion on this model is based on the delay term $\tau = 2.41$. Different values of τ were employed following the work of [Andersson and Lundberg \(1988\)](#). Therefore at $\tau = 2.41$, it is shown that increasing the values of temperature reduces the values of albedo as the solutions shows.

6.2 Further Work

The following areas can be explored on further studies

- how the systems of delay differential and partial delay differential equations can be used in climate models using the Haar wavelet numerical methods.
- how the systems of non-linear delay differential equations can be used in modelling climate.

7. Appendix

This section contains the codes used in this study.

Example (2.3.2):

```
from sympy import integrate, symbols
xi ,t, i = symbols('xi t i')
def phi(i,t):
    if i==0:
        return 1 #x(t)=1
    else:
        return phi(i-1,i-1)-integrate(phi(i-1,xi-1),(xi,i-1,t))
tmax=10;
x=[phi(j,t) for j in range(tmax+1)]
print('x(t)={}'.format(x))

# Figure 2.1/4.1

t= np.linspace(-1,10,1000)
conditions=[t<=0,t>0,t>1,t>2,t>3, t>4, t>5,t>6,t>7, t>8,t>9]
plt.plot(t,np.pieceswise(t,conditions,lambdas))
plt.xlabel('t',fontsize=10)
plt.ylabel('x(t)',fontsize=10)
plt.tick_params(labelsize=10)
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```

Example (2.3.3)

```
# Figure 4.2, for  $\tau=3$ :
# import pydelay and numpy and pylab
import numpy as np
import pylab as pl
# from pydelay import dde23

# define the equations
eqns = {
    'x' : '0.25 * x(t-tau) / (1.0 + pow(x(t-tau),p)) -0.1*x'
}

#define the parameters
params = {
    'tau': 3,
    'p' : 10
}

# Initialise the solver
dde = dde23(eqns=eqns, params=params)
```

```

# set the simulation parameters
# (solve from t=0 to t=1000 and limit the maximum step size to 1.0)
dde.set_sim_params(tfinal=1000, dtmax=1.0)

# set the history of to the constant function 0.5 (using a python lambda function)
histfunc = {
  'x': lambda t: 0.5
}
dde.hist_from_funcs(histfunc, 51)

# run the simulator
dde.run()

# Make a plot of x(t) vs x(t-tau):
# Sample the solution twice with a stepsize of dt=0.1:

# once in the interval [515, 1000]
sol1 = dde.sample(503, 1000, 0.1)
x1 = sol1['x']

# and once between [500, 1000-15]
sol2 = dde.sample(500, 1000-3, 0.1)
x2 = sol2['x']

pl.plot(x1, x2)
pl.xlabel('$x(t)$')
pl.ylabel('$x(t - 3)$')
pl.show()

Logistic Equation
Figure 4.3: for  $\tau = 15$ :

# import pydelay and numpy and pylab
import numpy as np
import pylab as pl
# from pydelay import dde23

# define the equations
eqns = {
  'x' : '0.25 * x(t-tau) / (1.0 + pow(x(t-tau),p)) -0.1*x'
}

#define the parameters
params = {
  'tau': 15,
  'p' : 10
}

```

```
# Initialise the solver
dde = dde23(eqns=eqns, params=params)

# set the simulation parameters
# (solve from t=0 to t=1000 and limit the maximum step size to 1.0)
dde.set_sim_params(tfinal=1000, dtmax=1.0)

# set the history of to the constant function 0.5 (using a python lambda function)
histfunc = {
    'x': lambda t: 0.5
}
dde.hist_from_funcs(histfunc, 51)

# run the simulator
dde.run()

# Make a plot of x(t) vs x(t-tau):
# Sample the solution twice with a stepsize of dt=0.1:

# once in the interval [515, 1000]
sol1 = dde.sample(515, 1000, 0.1)
x1 = sol1['x']

# and once between [500, 1000-15]
sol2 = dde.sample(500, 1000-15, 0.1)
x2 = sol2['x']

pl.plot(x1, x2)
pl.xlabel('$x(t)$')
pl.ylabel('$x(t - 15)$')
pl.show()

#Figure 4.4

import numpy as np
import pylab as pl
eqns = {
    'x' : ' mu * x * (1-x(t-tau1))'
}

params = {
    'tau1': 1,
    'mu' : 1.2
}

dde = dde23(eqns=eqns, params=params)
```

```
dde.set_sim_params(tfinal=1000, dtmax=0.1)
```

```
histfunc = {  
'x': lambda t: 0.1  
}  
dde.hist_from_funcs(histfunc)  
dde.run()
```

```
sol1 = dde.sample(1, 100, 0.1)  
x1 = sol1['x']  
sol2 = dde.sample(0, 100-1, 0.1)  
x2 = sol2['x']  
plt.plot(x1, x2)  
plt.xlabel('$x(t)$')  
plt.ylabel('$x(t - 1)$')  
plt.grid()  
plt.show()
```

```
# Figure 4.5
```

```
import numpy as np  
import pylab as pl  
eqns = {  
'x' : ' mu * x * (1-x(t-tau1))'  
}
```

```
params = {  
'tau1': 1.0,  
'mu' : 1.6  
}
```

```
dde = dde23(eqns=eqns, params=params)
```

```
dde.set_sim_params(tfinal=1000, dtmax=.1)
```

```
histfunc = {  
'x': lambda t: 0.1  
}  
dde.hist_from_funcs(histfunc)  
dde.run()
```

```
sol1 = dde.sample(0.7, 1000, 0.01)  
x1 = sol1['x']  
sol2 = dde.sample(0, 1000-0.7, 0.01)  
x2 = sol2['x']
```

```
plt.plot(x1, x2, 'b' )
```

```
plt.xlabel('$x(t)$')
plt.ylabel('$x(t - 2)$')
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```

#Figure 4.6

```
import numpy as np
import pylab as pl
eqns = {
    'x' : ' mu * x * (1-x(t-tau1))'
}
```

```
params = {
    'tau1': 2.0,
    'mu' : 1.51
}
```

```
dde = dde23(eqns=eqns, params=params)
```

```
dde.set_sim_params(tfinal=1000, dtmax=.1)
```

```
histfunc = {
    'x': lambda t: 0.1
}
dde.hist_from_funcs(histfunc)
dde.run()
```

```
sol1 = dde.sample(100, 1000, 0.01)
x1 = sol1['x']
sol2 = dde.sample(0, 1000-100, 0.01)
x2 = sol2['x']
```

```
plt.plot(x1, x2, 'b' )
plt.xlabel('$x(t)$')
plt.ylabel('$x(t - 2)$')
plt.grid()
plt.show()
```

Figure 4.7 and 4.8

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
eqns = {
    'T' : '(349.7 * (1 - a * ( T(t-tau))))/pow(1.52 * 10,8) - ((pow(5.67*10,-8) *
    g * pow(T,4)))/pow(1.52*10,8)'
}
```

```
params = {
'tau': 2.41,
'a' : 0.25,
'g' : 0.88
}

dde = dde23(eqns=eqns, params=params)
dde.set_sim_params(tfinal=1000, dtmax=1.0)

histfunc = {
'T': lambda t: 283.15
}
dde.hist_from_funcs(histfunc)
dde.run()

sol1 = dde.sample(-500, 100, 0.1)
x1 = sol1['T']

sol2 = dde.sample(0, 100+500, 0.1)
x2 = sol2['T']
plt.plot(x1, x2, 'b')
plt.xlabel('$T(T)$')
plt.ylabel('$\alpha^{\ast}T(T - 2.41)$')
plt.grid()
plt.show()

# codes for the values of a(T) and g(T)

import numpy as np

def a(T): # This is the albedo,  $\alpha^{\ast}(T)$ 
B=12
A=0.04
if T <= 216:
return 0.85
elif 216<=T<=283-B:
return 2.798-0.009*T
elif 283-B<=T<283:
return 2.798-0.009*T+ A*(1-np.cos(2*np.pi*(T-283-B)/B))
elif 283<=T:
return 0.25

def g(T): # This is the emmisivity function
m = 0.5
T_0=284.15
k = (1-m*np.tanh(T/T_0)**6)
return k
```

Acknowledgements

First of all, I would like to thank the LORD my God for the gift of life, without Him I would not have come this far. Secondly, I would like to express my utmost gratitude to my supervisor prof. Mohamed MBEHOU for all the academic support and guidance, and making it possible that this work maybe completed on time. I would also like to thank my tutor, Miss Alice Ikuzwe for her support and endless effort in making it possible that all could go in a right direction. Last but no the least, I would like to express my utmost gratitude to the entire African Institute for Mathematical sciences(AIMS) organization for giving me the opportunity to study.

References

- Andersson, L. S. and Lundberg, P. A. Delayed albedo effects in a zero-dimensional climate model. *Journal of the atmospheric sciences*, 45(16):2294–2305, 1988.
- Austin Gorens. Simplifying the climate system, 2020. URL <https://www.global-climate-change.org.uk/4-2.php>. [Online; accessed 18-April-2020].
- Aziz, I. and Amin, R. Numerical solution of a class of delay differential and delay partial differential equations via haar wavelet. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 40(23-24):10286–10299, 2016.
- Aziz, I., Haq, F., et al. A comparative study of numerical integration based on haar wavelets and hybrid functions. *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, 59(6):2026–2036, 2010.
- Aziz, I., Šarler, B., et al. Wavelets collocation methods for the numerical solution of elliptic bv problems. *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 37(3):676–694, 2013.
- Bellen, A. and Zennaro, M. *Numerical Methods for Delay Differential Equations*. CLARENDON PRESS, 2003.
- Bhattacharya, K., Ghil, M., and Vulis, I. Internal variability of an energy-balance model with delayed albedo effects. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 39(8):1747–1773, 1982.
- Buytaert, W., Célleri, R., , and Timbe, L. Predicting climate change impacts on water resources in the tropical andes: Effects of gcm uncertainty. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 36(7), 2009.
- CHUNG, H.-Y. and SUN, Y.-Y. Analysis of time-delay systems using an alternative technique. *International Journal of Control*, 46(5):1621–1631, 1987.
- Driver, R. D. *Ordinary and delay differential equations*, volume 20. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- Epstein, P. R. and McCarthy, J. J. Assessing climate stability. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 85(12):1863–1870, 2004.
- Flunkert, V. and Schoell, E. Pydelay-a python tool for solving delay differential equations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:0911.1633*, 2009.
- Ghil, M. and Bhattacharya, K. An energy-balance model of glaciation cycles. 1979.
- Goody, R. Polar process and world climate (a brief overview). *Monthly Weather Review*, 108(12): 1935–1942, 1980.
- Guest Blogger. What are climate models and how accurate are they?, 2020. URL <https://blogs.ei.columbia.edu/18/05/2018/climate-models-accuracy/>. [Online; accessed 18-April-2020].
- Hale, J. K., Lunel, S. M. V., Verduyn, L. S., and Lunel, S. M. V. *Introduction to functional differential equations*, volume 99. Springer Science & Business Media, 1993.
- Keane, A. and Postlethwaite, C. Climate models with delay differential equations. *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science*, 27:114309, 11 2017. doi: 10.1063/1.5006923.
- Kuang, Y. *Delay differential equations: with applications in population dynamics*. Academic press, 1993.

- Kyrychko, Y. and Hogan, S. On the use of delay equations in engineering applications. *Journal of vibration and control*, 16(7-8):943–960, 2010.
- Lynch, S. *Dynamical Systems with Applications Using Python*. Springer, 2018.
- Macy, M. and Tsvetkova, M. The signal importance of noise. *Sociological Methods & Research*, 44(2): 306–328, 2015.
- MarcR.Roussel. Dimension — Delay-differentialequations, 2005. URL <http://people.uleth.ca/~roussel/nld/delay.pdf>. [Online; accessed 25-April-2020].
- Parker, W. Climate science. In Zalta, E. N., editor, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, summer 2018 edition, 2018.
- Parrish, J. T. A brief discussion of the history, strengths and limitations of conceptual climate models for pre-quatarnary time. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences*, 341(1297):263–266, 1993.
- Rakshit, A., Singh, H. B., Singh, A. K., Singh, U. S., and Fraceto, L. New frontiers in stress management for durable agriculture, 2020.
- Robinove, C. J., Chavez Jr, P. S., Gehring, D., and Holmgren, R. Arid land monitoring using landsat albedo difference images. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 11:133–156, 1981.
- Schleussner, C.-F., Frieler, K., Meinshausen, M., Yin, J., and Levermann, A. Emulating atlantic overturning strength for low emission scenarios: Consequences for sea-level rise along the north american east coast. 2011.
- Sellers, W. D. A global climatic model based on the energy balance of the earth-atmosphere system. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, 8(3):392–400, 1969.
- Shampine, L. F., Thompson, S., and Kierzenka, J. Solving delay differential equations with dde23. URL <http://www.runet.edu/~thompson/webddes/tutorial.pdf>, 2000.
- Stocker, T. and Knutti, R. Do simplified climate models have any useful skill? *CLIVAR Exchanges*, 8, 01 2003.
- SULEIMAN, M. Two and three point one-step block methods for solving delay differential equations. *Journal of Quality Measurement and Analysis JQMA*, 8(1):29–41, 2012.
- U.S National Weather Service. What is el niño-southern oscillation (enso)?, 2020. URL <https://www.weather.gov/mhx/ensowhat>. [Online; accessed 20-April-2020].
- Wikipedia contributors. Climate — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Climate&oldid=955270222>, 2020a. [Online; accessed 12-May-2020].
- Wikipedia contributors. General circulation model — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=General_circulation_model&oldid=950740508, 2020b. [Online; accessed 11-May-2020].
- Wikipedia contributors. History of climate change science — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=History_of_climate_change_science&oldid=951799203, 2020c. [Online; accessed 1-May-2020].

Wilks, D. Effects of stochastic parametrization on conceptual climate models. *Philosophical transactions. Series A, Mathematical, physical, and engineering sciences*, 366:2477–90, 08 2008. doi: 10.1098/rsta.2008.0005.